

CELESTIAL IMAGE RECOGNITION ACROSS GALAXIES

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Abstract: Humans are really good at recognizing things they see, like objects in front of them. Our eyes and brains work together super quickly and accurately to do this, even with complicated tasks like figuring out what something is. The configurations and arrangements of galaxies offer vital insights into the origins and evolution of the universe. But it's tough for computers to automatically figure out what type of galaxy is in a picture because the images are often faint, there are bright stars in the background, and the pictures can be noisy. We came up with a way to help computers detect and classify galaxies automatically. Our method includes making the data more varied and stretching the contrast of the images. This helps the trained models work better with different kinds of data and produce more accurate results. We disclosed our approach as a component of an open-source initiative in computer vision, tailored specifically for scrutinizing extensive collections of galaxy images.

I. INTRODUCTION

At the beginning of the 20th century, scientists found galaxies, and since then, studying them has become a big deal in astronomy. This helps us learn a lot about how the universe started and changed over time. As technology improves, we're collecting more and more data about galaxies, which helps us understand them better. By looking at things like how stars move and the chemicals in galaxies, we can even estimate how old they are and what they've been through. This is really important for figuring out how the universe formed and evolved. In facilitating the differentiation of various galaxy types, scientists employ deep learning, a technology well-suited for processing large datasets. This methodology has also found application in diverse fields such as genetics and physics. For instance, deep learning can assist in detecting anomalous galaxies.

II. LITERATURE SURVEY

Mohamed Abd El Aziz, I. M. Selim, and Shengwu Xiong have devised a novel approach for automatically detecting galaxy morphology from datasets utilizing an image-retrieval methodology. While various classification methods exist for identifying galaxy types within images, some situations require not only determining the galaxy type in the queried image but also finding the most similar images to the query.

Hence, this study introduces an image-retrieval technique to identify galaxy types within an image and retrieve the most similar images. The proposed method comprises two stages: firstly, a set of features is extracted using shape, color, and texture descriptors, followed by a binary sine cosine algorithm to select the most pertinent features. Secondly, the similarity between the features of the queried galaxy image and those of other galaxy images is computed. Experiments were conducted using the FIGI catalogue, which includes approximately 5000 galaxy images of various types (edge-on spiral, spiral, elliptical, and irregular). [1].

Enrico M. Di Teodoro, J. E. G. Peek, John F. Wu developed a model by using a Deep Learning algorithm i.e., Convolution Neural Network. In this paper, we present and make available a new method to clean catalogs from galaxy shreds. A convolutional neural network (CNN) is trained on three-band optical images in order to identify whether objects in catalogs are galaxy fragments or genuine sources. The remainder of this paper is structured as follows. Section describes the data used in this work and the machine-learning algorithm used for identifying galaxy shreds. We apply our CNN to some of the most complete photometric catalogs available nowadays and discuss our findings in Section We summarize and conclude in Section. We adopted a machine-learning algorithm to identify galaxy shreds from multiband images. Individual star-formation regions within a galactic disk have very distinctive morphological features with respect to a galaxy as a whole. CNN is ideal to identify these features and classify objects based on their appearance. A CNN is a particular type of neural network that includes a number of layers performing convolution, which can be used to extract weighted features from input images for a given problem. In particular, our task is a simple binary classification problem i.e., whether a target is either a proper galaxy or just a shred of a galaxy [2].

R.E. Gonzalez, R.P. Munoz, and C.A. Hernandez developed the foundational model, employing convolutional neural networks and deep learning techniques, which typically yield superior results compared to methods reliant on manual feature engineering and SVMs, particularly with large training datasets. The efficacy of training outcomes is closely tied to the process of converting raw FITS data into a 3-channel color image for each band. Consequently, we propose data augmentation during training, employing five conversion methods. This significantly enhances the overall detection and classification of galaxies in images generated from various instruments, bands, and data reduction procedures. The detection and classification methods were trained utilizing the DARKNET deep learning framework and the YOLO real-time object detection system. These methods are coded in C language and optimized for the CUDA platform, leveraging graphical processing units (GPUs) extensively. [3].

Babatunde Keshinro implemented the model Using a set of labeled training images, a machine learning model is trained to recognize a set of target classes (items to detect in images). The challenging visual task of object detection necessitates anticipating both location of things in an image and the type of objects identified. It's critical to focus not only on identifying distinct images but also on estimating the concepts and locations of items in the image, in order to obtain a thorough knowledge of the image. In addition to identifying objects in an image, object segmentation also entails making mask for the image that identifies the pixels that make up the object. Initially, computer vision algorithms were fed raw pixel data. Classic computer vision models introduced new elements obtained from pixel data, such as color histograms, textures, and shapes, to model objects more flexibly. The disadvantage of this method is that feature engineering became a genuine pain due to the large number of inputs to adjust. Building robust models is difficult due to the fine-tuning of characteristics, and accuracy degrades as a result [4].

Mohamed Eassa, Ibrahim Mohamed Selim, Walid Dabour, and Passent Elkafrawy utilized a nonnegative matrix factorization algorithm to devise an automated supervised machine learning system for galaxy classification. This method underwent testing with two distinct datasets of galaxy images. In the case of the smaller dataset containing 110 images, it demonstrated an accuracy of approximately 93%. Meanwhile, with the larger dataset comprising 700 images, it achieved an accuracy rate of around 92%. [5].

John Jenkinson, Artyom Grigoryan, Mehdi Hajinoroozi, Raquel D'iaz Hernandez, Hayde Peregrina Barreto, Ariel Ortiz Esquivel, Leopoldo Altamirano and Vahram Chivichyan implemented the model that focuses on the application of the foregoing developed theory to autonomously classify galaxies in astronomical images. Astronomical data collection begins with the imaging of the sky by the camera. The telescope output is captured via a photographic plate, which is then digitized by a high-resolution scanner of 6400 dpi and 16 bits per pixel. A geometric calibration is performed to correct the deformation of the photographic emulsion and scanning errors. The digital image is then used to create a Flexible Image Transport System (FITS) format to be used for processing [6].

Alexander Khalil Arwadi, Aurelio Noca, and Louis Jaugey developed a model utilizing the SKA SDC1 dataset to train a machine learning model capable of galaxy detection within these images. The preprocessing techniques employed to clean the data are outlined, followed by a discussion on the model details and the machine learning approach utilized. Subsequently, the algorithm's performance is evaluated, alongside an analysis of the findings. Specifically, we opted to exclusively utilize images with an integration time of 1000 hours due to their lower noise levels compared to others. It's noteworthy that galaxies in the training set files are not uniformly distributed across the entire image span but are concentrated within approximately 1% of the simulated field. [7].

Joseph H. Murrugarra LL and Nina S. T. Hirata have presented initial findings on galaxy image classification employing convolutional neural networks (CNNs), achieving a classification accuracy slightly exceeding 90%. To advance this research and enhance the outcomes, we intend to address various factors. These include incorporating data from all five bands, implementing common data augmentation techniques such as rotations, minor translations, and image reflections. Additionally, we plan to integrate expert-designed features alongside CNN features, substitute the connected component extraction method with one based on the Petrosian radius available in catalogs, and expand the training set for improved results. [8].

III. PROBLEM STATEMENT

The problem statement defined as, " Identifying information related to galaxies is detected when a user uploads an image of a galaxy captured through an end-to-end application".

IV. PROPOSED ALGORITHM

The VGG16 is a convolutional neural network (CNN) architecture pioneered by the Visual Geometry Group (VGG). It was designed primarily for image classification tasks and became renowned for its straightforward yet powerful structure. The designation "16" in VGG16 denotes the overall number of layers within the network, encompassing convolutional layers, pooling layers, and fully connected layers. Precisely, VGG16 comprises 13 convolutional layers and 3 fully connected layers.

VGG16 can recognize things in pictures, it needs learning, just like how we can learn by looking at lot of pictures of dogs to recognize on, it learn by looking at thousands and thousands of pictures. Basically is used to understand what is in the picture.

Input Layer: Imagine you have a picture, like a photograph you take with a camera. This picture is what we start with, and it's made up of tiny squares called pixels, each containing color information.

Convolution Layers: Think of these layers as special filters that look at small parts of the picture at a time. They move across the entire image, bit by bit, looking for patterns like edges, shapes, or textures. These filters help the network understand what's in the picture.

Pooling Layers: After each set of filters, we want to simplify the picture a bit. Pooling layers do this by taking small squares of the image and condensing them into a single value. It's like zooming out a bit and getting a general idea of what's in that part of the picture.

Fully Connected Layers: Now that the network has seen different parts of the picture and understood some patterns, it's time to make sense of it all. These layers act like your brain, connecting all the information from the earlier layers and deciding what the picture is showing. It's like putting together all the clues to guess what the picture is.

Output: Finally, after going through all these layers, we get an answer. In the case of VGG16, the network tells us what it thinks is in the picture and how confident it is about that answer. For example, it might say, "I'm 90% sure this is a dog."

VGG16 looks at different parts of the picture, finds patterns, simplifies the information, puts it all together, and then makes a guess about what the picture shows.

V.METHODOLOGY

The initial step involves "validating" the model using a limited dataset. Following this, the model undergoes a "training" phase with a more extensive dataset, capturing its behavior across diverse situations and circumstances. After successful training, the model is ready for deployment. When presented with new data, it leverages its learned behavior to "predict" outcomes based on the input data. This description is simplified, recognizing that real-world applications involve various variations and nuances. As depicted in the straightforward process diagram above, data assumes a pivotal role throughout every phase of development and training. The data provided to the model not only influences the content of the model's output but also determines its effectiveness. In essence, the model's performance mirrors the quality of the input data.

VI. CONCLUSION

The implementation of the project could have been expanded to encompass a broader range of galaxy classes, including various types such as Spiral, Elliptical, Irregular, and Lenticular galaxies. Instead of solely predicting the name, shape, and contrast of galactic images, the system could have been designed to extract the entire sequence of information inherent in the data.

Furthermore, the project could have included galaxies within the observed regions of the sky. This would provide valuable context for understanding the distribution and clustering of galaxies, shedding light on the large-scale structure of the universe.

In summary, by adopting a more comprehensive approach that encompasses a wider range of galaxy classes, extracting detailed information from galactic images and integrating user management features, the project could have offered a more holistic and insightful experience for both users and researchers alike.

VII. REFERENCES

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